

TUNNEL EFFECT IN THE FIELD OF LASER RADIATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6344797>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 20th February 2022

Accepted: 25th February 2022

Online: 30th February 2022

KEY WORDS

*multiphoton ionization,
multiphoton absorption,
laser ionization of an
atom, tunnel breakdown
mechanism*

ABSTRACT

The paper describes the process of ionization of an atom in the field of laser radiation. To describe the tunnel breakdown mechanism, the Keldysh-Faisal-Ries models can be applied. The ionization of an atom in a constant field is considered as multiphoton absorption

One of the fundamental differences between multiphoton ionization and single-photon ionization is as follows. Since the energy of each light quantum in the multiphoton case can be very small, and hence the period of light oscillations is large, multiphoton ionization should, in the limit, go over to the case of ionization of an atom in a constant electric field.

As is known, field ionization is described by quantum mechanics as electron tunneling under a potential barrier. In other words, the ionization of an atom in a constant field can be considered as multiphoton absorption, when the energy of each individual photon tends to zero, and

the number of absorbed photons becomes infinite [1].

The condition for the emergence of a tunnel effect in an alternating field can be qualitatively understood as follows (Fig. 1). Due to coherence, laser radiation can be represented as a classical electromagnetic wave, and the magnetic component of the wave can be neglected. Then an electric field acts on the atomic electron, periodically changing in time with the frequency of laser radiation. If the electron has time to tunnel through the atomic potential well with depth U in one half-cycle of the field, it will be ionized in accordance with the laws of the tunneling effect described by formula (1).

$$N \propto \exp\left[-\frac{8\pi}{3h} \sqrt{mcU^2}\right] \quad (1)$$

Otherwise, as they say, the multiphoton regime will be realized, which is described by the formula

$$N \sim I^q \quad (2)$$

In this formula, m and e are the mass and charge of the electron, and U is the ionization potential of the atom [2]. Occurrence of a tunnel effect in an alternating field. For one half-cycle, the field in the vicinity of the atom changes from curve (1) to curve (2). If during this time the electron has time to "leak" through the potential barrier formed by the field of the atomic core and the laser field, a tunnel effect will occur; otherwise, the multiphoton regime is realized.

Figure 1. Scheme of electron tunneling through a quasi-static potential barrier in the direction of the field;

a) – atom in the absence of an external field, dashed line – dotted line – Coulomb potential,

b) an atom in a field of intensity F , the solid curve is a potential barrier. 0 is the atomic nucleus, E_i is the binding energy of an electron in an atom, V is the barrier

height, z is the coordinate along the field direction. At $V > E_i$, the above-barrier decay of the atom occurs

To describe the tunnel breakdown mechanism, it is better to apply the Keldysh-Faisal-Ries models as a theoretical method. Theoretical methods for describing the

process of nonlinear ionization of atoms are based on several basic laws that characterize this process. Let's list these patterns.

- High intensity of the radiation field, at which the process of non-linear ionization of atoms is realized; we are talking not only about the fields of subatomic ($F < F_a$), but also atomic ($F = F_a$) and superatomic ($F > F_a$) intensity.

- The need to describe the transitions of an electron occurring under the influence of two fields of comparable amplitude - the Coulomb field of the atomic core and the external radiation field.

- The need to take into account the perturbation of the atomic spectrum by an external ionizing field in the event of a resonant displacement of atomic states, or a non-resonant change in their energy due to the Stark effect.

- The possibility of using a semi-classical method for describing the interaction of an atom with a radiation field, in which the field is described in the language of classical physics, and the atom in the language of quantum mechanics. The possibility of describing radiation in the language of classical physics is due to the large number of coherent photons, under the influence of which the process of nonlinear ionization occurs.

- The impulsive nature of the radiation field of high intensity and the typical shape of the pulse, in which the duration of the front is of the order of the duration of the pulse itself. Numerically, the values of and lie in the range from nano- to femtoseconds. Thus, in the course of the theoretical description of n , the nature of the inclusion of the external field, which can

be both instantaneous and adiabatic, should be taken into account [3].

Obviously, with such a number of basic regularities, there is no hope of creating an analytical theoretical description of the process of nonlinear ionization of atoms. Accordingly, in principle, there are only two possibilities - the development of a numerical calculation method for fixed values of the parameters characterizing the atom and the radiation field, or the development of approximate methods of analytical description that are valid only in a certain range of changes in the main parameters, or when one or other basic regularities are neglected.

In addition to the above basic regularities, we will point out a number of significant points that determine the nature of the theoretical description of the process of nonlinear ionization of atoms.

Theoretical methods for studying the interaction of electromagnetic radiation with atoms are based on certain approximations for solving the Schrödinger equation for the "atom + radiation field" system. Since the field of electromagnetic radiation is turned on and off, the non-stationary Schrödinger equation with an initial condition corresponding to the absence of an electromagnetic field is a Cauchy problem (i.e., the problem of finding a solution to an equation that satisfies certain initial conditions). Its solution is expanded in terms of the unperturbed eigenfunctions of the system after the field is turned on, and the probabilities of various transitions are determined. In this case, the field of electromagnetic radiation is assumed to be classical, which corresponds to the actual setting of experiments on the interaction of laser radiation with atomic

systems [3]. Thus, the following conclusions can be drawn from this:

1. The analysis of literary sources has shown that the existing works devoted to the breakdown of liquids do not have a complete theory of the breakdown of liquids. The main electrical properties of liquids seem to be determined by the "short range order", i.e. the nature of the interaction of molecules with their nearest neighbors, as is the case with semiconductors.

2. Despite the difficulties associated with the lack of a complete theory of the breakdown of liquids, breakdown patterns were established. The main processes of

electrical breakdown of a liquid in the initial stage are multiphoton ionization, cascade, or avalanche ionization. The first electrons appear due to a frequency-dependent tunneling effect, at high frequencies the tunneling mechanism is equivalent to multiphoton ionization.

3. A breakdown using laser radiation can be obtained using photochemical substances or due to the nonlinear ionization of a substance.

4. The main parameters that affect the nature of the interaction of laser radiation with matter are the ionization potential of the substance and the intensity of laser radiation.

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